

International Conference on Data Mining and Machine Learning (DMML 2020)

August 22~23, 2020, Chennai, India

<https://www.cseij.org/dmml/index.html>

Scope & Topics

International Conference on Data Mining and Machine Learning (DMML 2020) will act as a major forum for the presentation of innovative ideas, approaches, developments, and research projects in the areas of Data Mining and Machine Learning. It will also serve to facilitate the exchange of information between researchers and industry professionals to discuss the latest issues and advancement in the area of Big Data and Machine Learning.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in Data Mining and Machine Learning.

Topics of Interest

Data mining foundations

- Parallel and Distributed Data Mining Algorithms
- Data Streams Mining
- Graph Mining
- Spatial Data Mining
- Text video
- Multimedia Data Mining
- Web Mining
- Pre-Processing Techniques
- Visualization
- Security and Information Hiding in Data Mining

Data mining Applications

- Databases
- Bioinformatics
- Biometrics
- Image Analysis
- Financial Modeling
- Forecasting
- Classification
- Clustering
- Social Networks
- Educational Data Mining

Knowledge Processing

- Data and Knowledge Representation
- Knowledge Discovery Framework and Process
- Including Pre- and Post-Processing
- Integration of Data Warehousing
- OLAP and Data Mining

- Integrating Constraints and Knowledge in the KDD Process
- Exploring Data Analysis
- Inference of Causes
- Prediction
- Evaluating
- Consolidating and Explaining Discovered Knowledge
- Statistical Techniques for Generation a Robust
- Consistent Data Model
- Interactive Data Exploration/Visualization and Discovery
- Languages and Interfaces for Data Mining
- Mining Trends, Opportunities and Risks
- Mining from Low-Quality Information Sources

Machine learning

- Machine Learning Applications
- Learning in knowledge-intensive systems
- Learning Methods and analysis
- Learning Problems
- Deep Learning

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the [Submission System](#) by **June 27, 2020**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the on conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology \(CS & IT\)](#) series (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **DMML 2020**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issues of the following journals.

- [International Journal of Data Mining & Knowledge Management Process\(IJDKP\)](#)
- [International Journal of Database Management Systems\(IJDMS\)](#)
- [Machine Learning and Applications: An International Journal\(MLAIJ\)](#)
- [International Journal of Web & Semantic Technology \(IJWesT\)](#)

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : June 27, 2020**
- Authors Notification : July 30, 2020
- Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : August 08, 2020

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us: dmml@cseij.org or dmmlconf@yahoo.com